

Studies on the Polarographic Reduction of Progesterone

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Progesterone gave a well defined slightly drawnout wave when studied polarographically. The process is irreversible and a continuous negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ is observed with increasing pH. The value of $k_{t,n}D^{-1/2}$ varies from 0.016 to 5.348 at the foot of the wave to the plateau indicating that the process is completely kinetically controlled at the foot of the wave but becomes diffusion controlled and reversible at the plateau. A tentative mechanism for the reduction process has been proposed.

THE direct polarographic reduction of conjugated keto steroids has been studied earlier¹ and it is reported that ketones with a conjugated double bond are directly reducible at the d. m. e. Wolfe, Hershberg and Fieser (*loc. cit.*) were the pioneers in the polarography of keto steroids and they introduced a method for assaying the 17-keto steroid. Eisenbrand and Picher² found it possible to determine polarographically some hormones such as, testosterone, progesterone, corticosterone and desoxycorticosterone, which contain keto group and conjugated double bonding $O=C-C=C-$. Barnett and Morris³ studied some water soluble steroidal hydrazones polarographically.

The polarographic reduction of keto steroids depends greatly on external factors such as pH, nature and concentration of buffer and solvent. Much of the early work on the α,β -unsaturated keto steroid was performed in unbuffered or poorly buffered systems. Adkins and Cox⁴ obtained reduction waves for cholesterone in 0.1 N ammonium chloride solutions. Later, Eiesenbrand and Picher (*loc. cit.*) observed the behaviour of several Δ^4 -3-keto steroid in 90% ethanol and 0.1 N LiCl.

Sartori and Bianchi⁵ reported the half wave dependence on pH for 17-ethinyl-testosterone and methyl testosterone, but did not describe any changes in the wave form or diffusion current with pH. Later, Zuman *et al*⁶ made a fairly exhaustive study on the behaviour of certain Δ^4 -3-keto steroids in 30-60% ethanol solutions buffered with Britton and Robinson buffer mixtures.

The present paper deals with the polarographic behaviour of a conjugated keto steroid, progesterone, in presence of phosphate buffer. The study has been carried out in two different supporting electrolytes, LiCl and KCl, and an attempt has been made to suggest a mechanism for the reduction process.

Experimental

Pure sample of progesterone (B. D. H.) was used in all the experiments. All other chemicals were of B. D. H. AR grade. Solutions were prepared in double distilled water and were deaerated by

bubbling pure nitrogen gas. The temperature was maintained at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using a thermostat.

Polarograms were taken at different pH by using phosphate buffer in presence of KCl or LiCl used as supporting electrolyte. A Toshniwal manual polarograph, in conjunction with a sensitive polyflex galvanometer was used. The half wave potential refers to the saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E). Pure distilled mercury was used in dropping mercury electrode and the capillary characteristics at mercury height of 35 cm was $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.031 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$ in 0.1 N KCl.

Results and Discussion

A well defined single step reduction of progesterone is observed when it is reduced at the d. m. e. The diffusion current varies linearly with increase in the concentration of progesterone and the plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ indicate the phenomenon as diffusion controlled.

Analysis of C-V curves indicates the irreversibility of the process which is further confirmed by the nature of log plots and the value of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ (Table 1; Fig. 1); when $\log(i - i_r)$ is plotted against $-E_{d.e.}$ an initial straight line followed by a curve, a characteristic of irreversible process, is obtained. The values of the product of transfer coefficient and the number of electrons involved in the reduction process, αn , have been determined (Table 1) which are in conformity with the irreversible nature of the reduction process.

The diffusion current is markedly affected by the nature of the supporting electrolyte and the half wave potential is almost the same in both the supporting electrolytes (-0.92 V vs S.C.E.). The half wave potential is unaffected by the concentration of the depolarizer. However, it changes with temperature, first it increases and then decreases with the rise in temperature. All the while, the temperature coefficient of half wave potential is more than 2 mV per degree as can be expected of an irreversible process. The diffusion current varies linearly with temperature and the temperature coefficient is $0.0903 \mu \text{ amp}$ per degree.

TABLE 1
 Conc. of progesterone = $2.4 \times 10^{-5}\%$
 Hg height = 35 cm
 Temp. = $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$
 Buffer = Phosphate buffer (Na_2HPO_4 and NaH_2PO_4)

Supporting electrolyte pH	0.1 M LiCl				0.1 M KCl			
	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volts)	$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ (Volts)	αn	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volts)	$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ (Volts)	αn
5.8	0.9030	0.84	0.14	0.1564	1.0960	0.88	0.16	0.2513
6.2	0.8382	0.84	0.20	0.1231	0.9997	0.89	0.18	0.1774
6.4	0.8062	0.88	0.22	0.1625	0.9675	0.90	0.20	0.1922
6.8	0.7417	0.90	0.26	0.1186	0.9030	0.90	0.24	0.2809
7.4	0.7095	0.92	0.22	0.1182	0.7417	0.92	0.24	0.1478
7.8	0.6450	0.96	0.28	0.1106	0.6450	0.94	0.26	0.1774
8.1	0.6127	0.98	0.28	0.1184	0.5808	0.98	0.28	0.1922

Fig. 1. C=V curves of progesterone at different pH.

A regular negative shift in half wave potential and decrease in diffusion current with increasing pH has been observed and a strict proportionality of both the factors with pH has been obtained

(Figs. 2, 3). The negative shift of half wave potential and the decrease in the value of the diffusion current may be due to the complexation of the depolarizer with the constituents of buffer.

Fig. 2. pH vs i_d .

Fig. 3. pH vs $-E_{1/2}$.

The values of the rate constant $k_{r,h}$ at different potentials have been calculated by Koutecky's method⁷. An increase in the value of $k_{r,h}$ with potential is observed and $-\log k_{r,h}$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$ plots are straight lines (Fig. 4). The value of $k_{r,h} D^{-1/2}$ varies from 0.016 to 5.348 (Table 2) with the increase in potential at the d. m. e. which clearly indicates that the electrode process is totally irreversible and kinetically controlled at the foot of the wave while it is reversible and diffusion controlled at the top. During the entire rising portion of the wave the process is controlled kinetically and by diffusion. The value of heterogeneous rate constant $k_{r,h}^0$ increases regularly with the increase in pH, indicating that the phenomenon becomes more and more reversible. The variation in free energy change with pH also supports this view. The value of $k_{r,h}^0$ first increases and then decreases with a rise in temperature and the value at 25° is maximum. This variation is in accordance with the shift in $E_{1/2}$ with temperature (Table 3).

Mechanism of polarographic reduction: Progesterone molecule possesses conjugated carbonyl group at 3-C atom and therefore, the electrolytic

Fig. 4. $-\log k_{r,h}$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$

TABLE 2

Supp. electrolyte pH	0.1 M LiCl					0.1 M KCl						
	$-E_{d.e.}$ (V)	$-\log k_{r,h}$	$k_{r,h} \times 10^5$	$k_{r,h} \times D^{-1/2}$	$k_{r,h}^0 \times 10^5$ (cm.sec ⁻¹)	ΔG (K cal)	$-E_{d.e.}$ (V)	$-\log k_{r,h}$	$k_{r,h} \times 10^5$	$k_{r,h} \times D^{-1/2}$	$k_{r,h}^0 \times 10^5$ (cm.sec ⁻¹)	ΔG (K cal)
5.8	0.5	4.7212	1.90	0.03042			0.7	4.3208	1.20	0.01921		
	0.6	4.6020	2.50	0.04003			0.8	3.9871	10.30	0.01649		
	0.7	4.2291	5.90	0.09447	3.1623	72.7955	0.9	3.6602	21.80	0.05860	3.1623	72.7955
6.2	0.8	3.8181	15.20	0.24339			1.0	3.3056	49.40	0.79103		
	0.9	3.4685	34.20	0.54763			1.1	3.0079	98.00	1.56925		
	0.5	4.7055	1.97	0.08154			0.7	4.4962	3.10	0.05108		
6.4	0.6	4.4089	3.90	0.06244			0.8	4.0640	8.60	0.06507		
	0.7	4.1938	6.40	0.10248	4.4668	71.9287	0.9	3.6223	23.80	0.38206	5.0119	71.6397
	0.8	3.9208	12.90	0.20680			1.0	3.3453	45.10	0.72281		
6.6	0.9	3.4229	47.20	0.75580			1.1	2.9875	115.4	1.84147		
	0.5	4.7212	1.99	0.08186			0.7	4.1898	3.23	0.05173		
	0.6	4.2676	5.40	0.08646			0.8	3.9847	10.35	0.16573		
6.8	0.7	4.0861	8.20	0.06542	6.3096	71.0619	0.9	3.6500	22.38	0.35886	7.9433	70.4840
	0.8	3.8860	13.70	0.21987			1.0	3.1436	71.83	1.15020		
	0.9	3.5528	28.80	0.44835			1.1	2.7945	254.3	4.06725		
7.4	0.5	4.6989	2.00	0.03202			0.7	4.6020	2.50	0.04003		
	0.6	4.4948	3.20	0.05124			0.8	3.9623	10.09	0.18156	25.0000	67.5946
	0.7	4.2144	6.10	0.09767	7.9433	70.4840	0.9	3.7841	16.43	0.25620		
7.8	0.8	3.8268	11.20	0.35068			1.0	3.5048	31.27	0.50072		
	0.9	3.6595	21.90	0.57966			1.1	3.3120	48.74	0.78046		
	0.5	4.6615	2.18	0.08490			0.7	4.5406	2.88	0.04611		
8.1	0.6	4.4698	3.39	0.05428			0.8	4.2168	3.04	0.04867	50.0000	65.8609
	0.7	4.2021	6.27	0.10040	14.000	69.039	0.9	3.9809	11.72	0.18767		
	0.8	3.9390	11.75	0.18815			1.0	3.6822	32.92	0.52746		
8.1	0.9	3.6988	20.00	0.32025			1.1	3.4899	64.57	1.09394		
	0.5	4.7173	1.90	0.08069			0.7	4.3191	2.40	0.08849		
	0.6	4.6182	2.40	0.08843			0.8	4.1538	7.01	0.11284	79.0000	64.7053
8.1	0.7	4.4105	3.80	0.06222	17.000	68.5192	0.9	3.8711	13.45	0.21537		
	0.8	4.1419	7.20	0.11548			1.0	3.5442	28.55	0.36597		
	0.9	3.8576	13.80	0.20816			1.1	3.2478	71.14	1.13713		
8.1	0.5	4.7117	1.90	0.03106			0.7	4.4462	1.55	0.05729		
	0.6	4.5905	2.50	0.04110			0.8	4.2289	11.17	0.09562	126.0000	63.5494
	0.7	4.3822	4.10	0.06642	50.000	65.8609	0.9	3.9586	20.38	0.17886		
8.1	0.8	4.1126	7.70	0.12355			1.0	3.7085	49.19	0.78778		
	0.9	3.8183	15.10	0.24328			1.1	3.4000	125.88	2.00160		

TABLE 3

 Conc. of progesterone = 1.6×10^{-6} %
 Hg height = 35 cm
 pH = 7.4

Supporting electrolyte	0.1 M LiCl				0.1 M KCl			
	Temp. (°C)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volt)	$k_{f,h}^0 \times 10^8$ (cm. sec ⁻¹)	ΔG (K cal)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volt)	$k_{f,h}^0 \times 10^8$ (cm. sec ⁻¹)
15	0.7740	0.90	5.0119	68.75038	0.8062	0.90	5.0119	71.63978
20	0.9330	0.96	6.3096	71.06190	0.8757	0.92	6.3096	71.06190
25	0.9675	0.98	40.0000	66.43886	0.9352	0.94	16.0000	68.75038
30	1.8867	0.92	32.0620	67.01674	1.2320	0.90	13.0000	69.32826
35	1.4500	0.90	7.9433	70.48402	1.4512	0.86	7.9433	70.48402

Progesterone

reduction of this molecule can take place in a manner similar to that of unsaturated conjugated ketones. One electron bimolecular reduction process is possible which proceeds through a coupling reaction resulting in the formation of a pinacol.

The probability of reduction of second carbonyl group attached at 20-C atom is comparatively less because this carbonyl group lacks conjugation and

is sterically more hindered than carbonyl group of C-3 atom. Further, this reduction is difficult as it requires more energy for fission of side chain at C-17 atom from the pentenophenanthrene nucleus. Similar mechanism had been proposed by Kabasakalian and McGlotten⁸ for the polarographic reduction of Δ^4 -3-keto steroids.

References

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